

A PRACTICAL GUIDE · HPC + BIOINFORMATICS

Containers for Nextflow

on HPC

Reproducible pipelines without dependency hell.

Dr Sarah Beecroft

Supercomputing Specialist, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre

“It worked on my laptop”

Three sentences every bioinformatician has heard - or said.

“I can't reproduce the figures from the 2023 paper. Half the tools won't install on the new cluster.”

— PhD student

“Why does the same pipeline give different variant calls on Setonix vs. our old node?”

— PI

“How can I ship my software stack for Reviewer 2 so I can get the paper published?”

— Postdoc

The plan

Concepts → tooling → wiring it into Nextflow → surviving on the cluster.

1

Why containers

The reproducibility argument in a nutshell

2

Singularity on HPC

Why not Docker, and the commands that matter

3

Nextflow ↔ containers

Process directives and the config file

4

Image sources

BioContainers and where to find them

5

HPC gotchas

Caches, binds, scratch, network, GPUs

6

A working config

Copy-paste-able starting point

1.

2.

3.

4.

5.

6.

BIOINFORMATICS
REPRODUCIBILITY:

HOW HARD COULD IT BE?

Bioinformatics has a dependency problem

Containers fix the four pains that eat the most of our time.

Version drift

BWA 0.7.17 vs 0.7.18 changes alignment in edge cases. Containers pin one version.

Installation pain

Fighting with installs or looking for deprecated software versions. Containers are the complete environment, locked down

Cluster sprawl

Each cluster has different module versions. Containers run identically anywhere.

Audit trail

An image digest is a hash. Cite it and rerun the exact same software in 5 years.

Container Explainer

Key concepts about how containers work

Regular Install vs Container

*Each tool shares libraries and dependencies.
Quickly becomes 'dependency hell'*

Tools don't share anything except the OS

BUNDLED TOGETHER

Everything your software needs

CONCEPT

Container Engines

User issues commands to the Container Engine, which executes tasks using the Container

Singularity Engine is best for HPC

! *The Docker Engine was designed for cloud computing and needs sudo access* **!**

Concern	Docker	Singularity
Privileges	Daemon runs as root	Runs as you, no daemon
Image format	Layered tarballs in /var	Single .sif file you can move around
Filesystem	Bind mounts, but root-owned	Auto-binds \$HOME, \$PWD, /tmp

Bottom line: Singularity was designed for unprivileged users on shared filesystems. That's us.

Singularity & Docker Containers

*Singularity and Docker can also be used to **create** containers*

Syntax

Both Singularity and Docker have different syntax for writing container recipes

File extension

Each has different file extension. Singularity is .sif

Standard

Docker containers are the de facto standard.

Singularly flexible

Singularity can run **both** types of container

Tip: Typical setup is using the Singularity engine to pull and run Docker containers

BioContainers

An automated build of every Bioconda recipe: One tool per image, indexed by version + hash.

9,000+

bioinformatics tools

packaged automatically from Bioconda

Most nf-core pipelines will already have
containers prepared for you

Finding an image

1. Search biocontainers.pro
See also: quay.io and hub.docker.com
2. Pin the version
`samtools:1.20--h50ea8bc_0`
3. Cite by digest
`@sha256:a1b2c3...` → reproducible forever

Singularity in 60 seconds

```
$ singularity pull docker://quay.io/biocontainers/samtools:1.20--h50ea8bc_0
```

Convert any Docker/OCI container to a local singularity container (.sif extension)

```
$ singularity exec samtools_1.20.sif samtools view -h aln.bam
```

Run one command inside the image. Most common in pipelines

```
$ singularity shell samtools_1.20.sif
```

Interactive shell inside the container for poking around

```
$ singularity inspect samtools_1.20.sif
```

Read the labels, build date, and runscrip baked into the image

Most files are invisible to container

Default behaviour

- Cannot see directories outside \$PWD

With "bind mounting"

- Enables read/write to selected directories

```
$ singularity exec --bind /data/human samtools_1.20.sif view -h /data/human/aln.bam
```

Bind the directory you want the container to see

Nextflow Config

Refresher on Nextflow config optimisation

What is nextflow.config?

The single source of truth for how a pipeline runs — separate from what it does.

A plain text file in Groovy syntax

Nextflow reads it on every run

It controls everything outside the science:

- Executor, queues, resources
- Container engine and image cache
- Per-process specs
- Pipeline parameters and report outputs

Order of priority

1. Command-line: `-c custom.config`

2. Pipeline: `nextflow.config`

3. User: `~/.nextflow/config`

4. Built-in defaults

Higher layers win on conflicts.

Rule of thumb: `main.nf` says what to run; `nextflow.config` says where, with what, and how much.

What is a profile?

A named bundle of settings you switch on at launch

Anatomy of a profile

```
profiles {  
  standard {  
    process.executor = 'local'  
    docker.enabled   = true  
  }  
  
  slurm {  
    process.executor   = 'slurm'  
    singularity.enabled = true  
  }  
  
  cloud {  
    process.executor = 'awsbatch'  
    docker.enabled   = true  
  }  
}
```

Why profiles exist

One pipeline. Many places to run it.

Laptop, HPC, cloud: same code, different surroundings.

Pick at launch:

```
nextflow run main.nf -profile slurm
```

Stack them with commas:

```
-profile singularity,slurm
```

Later profiles override earlier ones.

Profiles separate ‘what’ from ‘how’

Same pipeline, different runtime options. Mix and match for your needs

-profile docker

Runs on your laptop

Enables Docker usage

-profile singularity

Runs on any HPC with Singularity

Enables Singularity usage

-profile slurm

Runs on Slurm cluster

Enables Slurm integration

-profile Pawsey_setonix

Runs on Pawsey’s Setonix system specifically

Enables Slurm and Singularity optimised for Setonix

```
$ nextflow run main.nf -profile singularity,slurm
```

Enabling Singularity

The minimal profile example. Drop this into nextflow.config

```
// nextflow.config
profiles {
    singularity {
        singularity.enabled = true
        singularity.autoMounts = true

        // May need to enable Singularity module
        process.module = "singularity/4.1.0-nompi"
    }
}
```

singularity.enabled = true

Turns on the Singularity engine for every process.

singularity.autoMounts = true

Auto-binds \$PWD, \$HOME, /tmp. Almost always what you want.

process.module

Loads system module singularity

Optional extras

Usually not needed

```
// nextflow.config
profiles {

    singularity {

        singularity.pullTimeout = "10 min"

        singularity.cacheDir    = "/scratch/$USER/.nf-cache"

        singularity.runOptions = "--bind /refs"

    }

}
```

pullTimeout

Time before pull is terminated

cacheDir

Where .sif files are stored. Usually managed by SysAdmins in background

runOptions

Extra flags. E.g. bind /refs directory

Container env variables worth knowing

These override nextflow.config and propagate to every job. SysAdmins should have configured for you

Variable	What it does
NXF_SINGULARITY_CACHEDIR	Where Nextflow stores pulled .sif files. Overrides singularity.cacheDir in config.
SINGULARITY_CACHEDIR	Singularity's own cache (used by `singularity pull` outside Nextflow).
SINGULARITY_TMPDIR	Where Singularity unpacks images during build/pull.
NXF_OFFLINE	Stops Nextflow from checking online on compute nodes without internet

```
export NXF_SINGULARITY_CACHEDIR=/scratch/$USER/.nf-cache
export NXF_OFFLINE=true
```

Nextflow Integration

Nextflow and containers working together

One container per process

Each process runs in its own image. Mix and match across the DAG - no global environment.

Each process declares its own image. Nextflow handles the pull, the exec, and the bind mounts.

Why this is good: a samtools update in one process can't break GATK in another.

The container directive

One line in your process. Nextflow does the rest.

```
process FASTQC {  
    container 'quay.io/biocontainers/fastqc:0.12.1--hdfd78af_0'  
  
    input:  
    path reads  
  
    output:  
    path "*_fastqc.html"  
  
    script:  
    """  
    fastqc $reads  
    """  
}
```

container

Image URL: Docker, quay.io, ghcr, or a local .sif path.

Resolved per-process

Different processes can use different images.

Nextflow caches

Pulls once into singularity.cacheDir, reuses everywhere.

Bind mounts

\$PWD, work/, and any inputs are auto-mounted.

Pinning images per process

Override the container directive from a single place - handy when forking a public pipeline.

```
// nextflow.config

process {

    withName: BWA_MEM {
        container = 'quay.io/biocontainers/bwa:0.7.18--he4a0461_0'
    }

    withLabel: process_with_GATK {
        container = 'quay.io/biocontainers/gatk4:4.5.0.0--py36hdfd78af_0'
    }

    // Default for everything else
    container = 'quay.io/biocontainers/bcftools:1.20--h8b25389_0'
}
```

withName

Match a specific process by name.

withLabel

Match every process tagged with a label.

default

Bare container = applies to all processes.

Beware the 'latest' tag

Using the container hash provides best reproducibility. Using latest is the worst

```
// nextflow.config
process {
  withName: BWA_MEM {
    container = 'quay.io/biocontainers/bwa:0.7.18--he4a0461_0'
  }
  withLabel: process_with_GATK {
    container = 'quay.io/biocontainers/gatk4:latest'
  }
}
```

Tags matter

The latest tag is just the most recent.

What's under the hood will change over time, ruining your reproducibility!

Adding container options per process

Allows you to add some tweaks to your container command as needed

```
process GPU_INFERENCE {  
    container 'nvcr.io/nvidia/pytorch:23.10-py3'  
    containerOptions '--nv'  
}  
  
process NEEDS_EXTRA_BIND {  
    container 'quay.io/biocontainers/fastqc:0.12.1--hdfd78af_0'  
    containerOptions '--bind /reference_data:/refs --bind /scratch'  
}
```

NVIDIA GPUs

Can add the --nv flag

Bind mounting

Ensure container can see special directories if needed

Flexible

Can put other flags here as needed

GPU passthrough.

DeepVariant, AlphaFold, Dorado, Bonito - the GPU has to be visible inside the container.

```
process {
  withLabel: gpu {
    clusterOptions = '--gres=gpu:1'
    accelerator    = 1
  }
}

singularity {
  enabled      = true
  autoMounts  = true
  runOptions  = '--nv --bind /scratch'
}
```


--nv flag

Singularity's --nv binds the host's NVIDIA driver and CUDA libs into the container.

The image still needs the matching CUDA toolkit baked in.

Pull once, run a thousand times

Nextflow will pull your containers when you first run the pipeline

1

Main Nextflow process

Pulls all images

2

.sif cache

Stored on HPC filesystem. Every task sees the same file(s).

3

Nextflow sub-tasks

No pull needed. Singularity just exec's the .sif, instantly.

Issues pulling images

Commons gotchas when Nextflow pulls images

No internet on compute nodes

Singularity tries to pull from quay.io

Task fails after 30 min — Nextflow retries — fails again

Pre-pull images

```
$ nextflow run main.nf \  
-profile singularity \  
-preview
```


OOM on main NF task

Pulling images can be memory-hungry

Sometimes main NF task will crash

Request enough mem

```
#SBATCH --mem 4GB
```

Pre-configured Setonix profile

Example of a real-world HPC config, available with `--profile pawsey_setonix`

```
// Enable use of Singularity to run containers
singularity {
    enabled      = true
    autoMounts  = true
}
// Submit up to 1024 concurrent jobs
executor {
    queueSize = 1024
}
// Define process resource limits
process {
    resourceLimits = [
        memory: 230.GB,
        cpus: 64
    ]
    executor      = 'slurm'
    clusterOptions = "--account=${System.getenv('PAWSEY_PROJECT')}}"
    module        = 'singularity/4.1.0-slurm'
    cache         = 'lenient'
    stageInMode   = 'symlink'
    queue = { task.memory <= 230.GB ? 'work' : 'highmem' }
}
```

THANK YOU

Questions?

Resources to pin to your wiki

Singularity docs

singularity.org/docs

BioContainers

biocontainers.pro

nf-core configs

github.com/nf-core/configs

Nextflow container docs

nextflow.io/docs/latest/container.html

Seqera Containers / Wave

seqera.io/containers

Nextflow Slack

nextflow.slack.com